

A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN MARGARET ATWOOD'S THE HANDMAID'S TALE AND KAZUO ISHIGURO NEVER LET ME GO

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Abstract:

Margaret Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale* and Kazuo Ishiguro's *Never Let MeGo* are dystopian novels which tells about loss of human and also humanism. Both the novels are visualised in this current century and depicts the life of human where surrogate mothers as well as loss of fertilisation and in the later novel about the development of cloning. Instead of these, both the novels depict about the development and significance of technology and the damage caused due to over usage of technology. Also deploys the man-made corruption to the environment. There are more similarities in these novels like the narrative style, the development of plot and characterisation.

Key Words: Similarity, Dystopian, Corruption, Environment, Humanism.

A Comparative study in Margaret Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale* and Kazuo Ishiguro's *Never Let Me Go*:

The Handmaid's Tale and *Never Let Me Go* are dystopian novels which portrays the loss of humanism. Both the novels display the growth of surrogate mothers and cloning in this twenty first century respectively. In these novels the protagonists are left unnoticed and their psychic changes occurs due to the external human. the protagonists are considered as sub- humans and are being used by human for their well- being. The sufferers are scapegoats for human to modify themselves. Greedy human modifies the fertile female to increase their population in *The Handmaid's Tale* and in the other novel human produces their models, that is the human models to fulfil human incompleteness by completing the clones. To which Atwood comments;

The outer world wants these children to exist because it's greedy for the benefits they can confer, but it doesn't wish to look head-on at what is happening. We assume- though it's never stated- that whatever objections might have been raised to such a scheme have already been overcome: by now the rules are in place and the situation is taken for granted- as slavery was once- by beneficiaries and victims alike. (Beedham 138)

Fertilization is the more similar concept in both the novels, in the former, the fertile female is imprisoned and used for human production. In the other novel, human produces human models for their use but the only thing the clone lack is fertilization. This is because, the human community is afraid by one or for the one they are in need. In the former, the totalitarian government is afraid that the healthy female will abduct pregnancy and the elite people will lose their generation and the people with low economic state will capture their position.

In the later, the hierarchical human makes the predominant human models to confine their life in a defined space and complete their life in a defined period. This method is progressed, because the dominant human in this novel does not want the clones to taste the real essence of life which would make them to hunger for freedom and they may want to have a pleasant life without enslaving for human community. This fear for luxury in human makes the clone in loss of fertilization. In both the areas the human is in fear for loss of power over others.

The need of human increases results in suppression of all other being including their own community who is deviated from their norms for being human. Both the authors handle the same elements to elucidate various themes. Apart from distinction there are more similarities in both dystopian novels. Most significantly both novelists' stresses on war that harms many. In the former, there is war that is running around Gilead and the updation is not given to the citizens of Gilead. The same thing happens in the novel *Never Let Me Go* there is lack of information about the day to day happening of the world outside their settlement. The linkage of war in this novel is that, the clones are produced to complete the human who are pretentious in war.

In the former men's prayvaganza is held to celebrate victory. The victory which they get by defeating the other in brutal rival. In the later novel, the war remains the starting point for the production of clones for the usage of human. In both the novels, war is noted as a starting point for creation of handmaids as well as

clones. In Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale*, war is also one of the reasons to segregate handmaids because of the destruction it has made in the life of human as well as the environment. The creation itself tells about their manipulation of their life.

The sub-humans in these novels are segregated in a centre and are fed up with the things needed to the human. Handmaids in Racheal and Leah centre and the clones in separate centres like Hailsham in which the protagonist and her friends live. This segregation makes the human to watch them in the easiest way and the human makes them understand their duty to serve human needs.

The narrative style of these novels slowly describes the place they live. Offred describes about Gilead and its norms and Kathy about Hailsham. Society terms the human as the same both the societies have created the norms and makes their needy beings to insert in their regulations. Both the societies create an identity in which the sub-humans are made to live. The sub-human's dreams are also wasted and it becomes useless in their made social norms.

Both protagonists of the novels are mentally free. From the beginning of the novel to the end both the protagonist accepts what comes to them. Both of them are physically mute because they are mentally sturdy. Both does not want to risk their life by raising a protest against the norms. In these novels, the protagonists have a trusted friends circle, Offred in *The Handmaid's Tale* has Moira and Ishiguro also introduces a character named Moira, though her appearance in this novel is limited it teaches the practicality to Kathy. Moira in both the novels are experienced and learns the right way for their life.

"I'm still here, you can see me. Anyway, look at it this way: it's not so bad, there's lots of women around. Butch paradise, you might call it." (Atwood 261)

"Don't talk rubbish. It's just another of Ruth's made-up things, that's all." (Ishiguro 55)

The protagonists in these novels has their own theory and works on them. Their theory is testified in some cases. Their theory makes them to think themselves as some other creatures in the eyes of human which they can use for their wish and also of the creature to which the human is afraid of their presence respectively. Offred thinks herself as a dog to the commander, for which in a situation Offred finds that the previous Handmaid is dead because of commander's action towards her. Now the commander has found another handmaid in the same place. For which Offred thinks that, "if your dog dies, get another" (Atwood 197).

Kathy thinks herself and her friends as spiders in the eyes of their Madame. When Ruth (Kathy's friend) says that their Madame is afraid of the them (the students at Hailsham), they frame a theory to find the truth. As per the theory they gave an unexpected appearance to their Madame. The sudden appearance of them makes her to get panic. For which Kathy says,

Madame was afraid of us. But she was afraid of us in the same way someone might be afraid of spiders. We hadn't been ready for that. It had never occurred to us to wonder how we would feel, being seen like that, being the spiders. (Ishiguro 35)

Apart from characterisation and plot, the symbolisation of dark remains unique in these novels. The darkness in their life does not only views about the cruelty and brutality human have made in their life but also the corruption of human mind by the evil thoughts.

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